

Bugun biz tez sur'atlar bilan o'zgarayotgan oldingi davrlardan tubdan farq qiladigan o'ta shiddatli va murakkab bir zamonda yashamoqdamiz. Globalashuv bu eng avvalo, hayot sur'atlarining beqiyos darajada tezlashuvi jamiyat hayotining barcha sohalariga bevosita ta'sir etayotgani bilan belgilanadi.⁵

O'zbekiston respublikasi birinchi prezidenti Islom Abdug'anovich Karimov "Yuksak ma'naviyat yengilmas kuch" asarida shunday yozgan edi, "Ayni paytda hayot haqiqati shuni ko'rsatadiki, har qanday taraqqiyot mahsulidan ikki xil maqsadda ezgulik va yovuzlik yo'lida foydalanish mumkin "

"Ommaviy madaniyaning" badiiy qiymati xalq madaniyatidan pastroq bo'ladi. Lekin uning auditoriyasi kengroq, chunki u muallifli, u odamlarning shu daqiqadagi ehtiyojini qondiradi, har qanday voqea hodisalarga hozirjavob bo'ladi. Ma'lum vaqt o'tgach, ular o'z dolzarbligini yo'qotadi. Hozirgi zamon yoshlari ongi shu darajadagi ular yon atrofidagi bo'layotgan voqea hodisaga fikr bildirib o'sha ishni qilishini hohlashadi. Yoshlar bilan ularga tushunarli bo'lgan o'rtacha tilda muloqot va madaniyat usullarining muhim jihati hisoblanadi. Bundan tashqari boshqa jihatlari ham bor. Boshqacha aytganda ko'pchilik jamiyat azolarining ongi pastligi, masalan 3-4-yil avval oldin ijtimoiy tarmoqlarda ko'plab baxs-munozaralarga duch kelgan yosh avlodni o'z domiga tortgan "Ko'k kit" o'yini ham ko'p o'smirlarni hayotiga xavf solgan hisoblanadi. Axborot texnologiyasi vositalarining ro'li tobora kuchayib ketganligi bois bo'sh o'ta sayoz madaniyat mahsulotlari ham bozorga chiqarilib yovuz kimsalar uni o'z maqsadida foydalanishmoqda.³

"Har narsa insonni o'ziga bog'liq" deganlaridek ommaviy madaniyat, media savodxonlik ijobiy shaklda foydalanayotganlar ham ko'p. Hozirgi kunda ham davlatimiz oliy ta'lim muassasalarida barcha axborot resurslari bor. Ulardan foydalanishni bilish kerak deb hisoblanadi. Chunki kelajak avlodga pedagog bir narsani tushuntirish uchun albatta o'ziga yangi metod kerak bo'ladi. Axborot texnologiyalaridan foydalanish ham yangilik hisoblanadi. Yoshlarning ommaviy madaniyati ananaviy qadriyatlarini tizimini ongli ravishda rad etishini va ularni qarama-qarshi qadriyatlar bilan almashtirishni talab qiladi. Qarama-qarshi madaniyat tomonidan taklif qilingan va prognoz qilingan shaxs har qanday axloqiy taqiq va axloqiy hokimiyatga dushman bo'lganligi sababli, chunki inson dunyosidagi axloqiy hokimiyatga dushman bo'lganligi sababli, chunki inson dunyosidagi axloqiy va manaviy yo'nalish qadriyatlarini mexanizmlari unig psixikasida hali to'liq shakllanmagan.⁴

Shunday qilib, bir tomondan, yoshlarning ommaviy madaniyatlarini kattalar jamiyatiga, uning qadriyatlarini va hokimiyatlariga qarshi norozilik rivojlantirsa, ikkinchi tomondan aynan ular yoshlarning o'sha jamiyatga moslashishiga hissa qo'shishga chiqarildi.

Ommaviy axborot vositalaridan foydalanish inson uchun ham foydali ham zararli oqibatli bor. Hozirgi kun talabi bo'yicha ommaviy axborot vositalaridan foydalanish shart lekin uni yomon maqsadlarda emas rivojlanish metod yo'lida foydalanish kerak hisoblanadi.

Yuqorida ta'kidlanganidek bugungi dunyoning ma'naviy qiyofasiga nazar tashlasak ahloqsizlikni, madaniyatsizlikni ma'naviyatsizlikni erkinlik deb bilish milliy urf-odatlar va qadriyatlarni mensimasdan, eskilik sarqiti deb qarash bilan bog'liq holatlar ma'naviy hayotga oila muqaddasligiga va yoshlar tarbiyasiga juda ham katta ta'sir ko'rsatib xavf solmoqda.

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